

THE ROLE OF “SMART CITIES” IN THE PROBLEMS OF URBAN ECOLOGY AND THEIR MODERN SOLUTIONS

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Annotation. The emergence of the concept of urban ecology is the result of many years of development. The perception of cities as an entire ecosystem was formed as a result of the influence of the population living in cities on it. Migrants, often migrating to different places, the urbanization of villages the increase in environmental problems in the general plan of cities had a significant impact on the change in the ecological life of cities. Also, an important problem cannot be considered a change in the atmosphere of cities as a result of the development of industry, economic development in states. This article discusses the emergence of urban ecology and problems in it.

Keywords: “Eco-city”, “green roofs”, ecosystem, urban ecology, “Smart city”.

УДК:711(25)

РОЛЬ «УМНЫХ ГОРОДОВ» В ПРОБЛЕМАХ ГОРОДСКОЙ ЭКОЛОГИИ И ИХ СОВРЕМЕННЫЕ РЕШЕНИЯ

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Аннотация. Появление понятия градостроительной экологии-результат многолетних разработок. Восприятие городов как целой экосистемы сформировалось в результате влияния на нее населения, живущего в городах. Значительное влияние на изменение экологической жизни городов оказали мигранты, часто мигрирующие в разные места,

урбанизация деревень увеличение экологических проблем в генеральном плане городов. Также немаловажной проблемой нельзя считать изменение атмосферы городов в результате развития промышленности, экономического развития в государствах. В данной статье обсуждалось возникновение градостроительной экологии и проблемы в ней.

Ключевые слова: Градостроительство, “Эко-город”, “зеленые крыши”, экосистема, городская экология, “Умный город”.

Introduction. Serious research into urban ecology began after the 1972 Stockholm conference. It was then that the term “urban planning ecology” was first coined by scientists. The concept of “eco-city” arose, which meant that cities would merge with nature in a harmonious balance.

Over the past 20 years, the field of urban ecology has undergone tremendous changes. Now with this term, broader concepts have begun to be understood. As the world is undergoing a process of accelerated urbanization, settlements have become a small number of ecosystems, and as a result of their globalization, the number of individual ecosystems has significantly decreased. This means that now an ecosystem covers a huge territory. These processes make it necessary for scientists of the large scientific community to seriously focus on this area. The difference between the urban ecosystem and other ecosystems is that it significantly undermines ecology as a result of involuntary or unintentional human impacts.

Methods. Today, in many developed countries of the world, the change in natural ingredients between cities and industrial zones, energy problems arising from the rapid expansion of cities, cause serious attention from the world community.

While the initial conclusions of the work of studying the structure and functioning of urban ecosystems were reached as a result of the research of cities and specific environmental processes in them, the causes and consequences of

urbanization, their interactions contribute to a new principled understanding of urban ecosystems. In this case, various solutions are being developed to eliminate the problems that arise based on the conclusions obtained from the ecological comparison of large cities with each other.

Discussion and results. Cities around the world are struggling with many environmental problems. In particular, air pollution in growing cities, changes in water and soil composition, a significant decrease in natural resources, the rapid obsolescence of urban infrastructure are proof of our words. The elimination of these problems requires the development of new measures and methods. As a result, serious attention is paid to the work of creating a new infrastructure. Gill, Tzoulas and others have actively researched areas of habitat conservation(2007);Newman, Kennedy, and others in the areas of urban metabolism (2011, 2015). Cities are increasingly showing biodiversity. The areas of monitoring the effectiveness of greenhouse gases, “green roofs”, biological protection systems, green infrastructure are of particular importance in the practice of Urban Ecology Research. The final task before scientists will be to solve increasingly advanced tasks in the practice of urban planning, design and monitoring (see Eco-Urban Project, which is planned to be built in Saudi Arabia).

The most important of the environmental problems in cities today are the following:

- providing drinking water to cities;
- management of wastewater;
- solid (difficult to process) and non-combustible waste;
- sharp increase in energy demand;
- disappearance of green spaces and natural landscapes;
- urban area expansion;
- soil pollution (melioration problems);
- increased traffic in cities;

- increased noise in urban centers;
- air pollution as a result of harmful gases emanating from vehicles, etc.

All these problems are a serious problem, especially for countries that are developing and in transition, in the current economic complex situations. In large cities of economically developed countries, problems with industrial production, housing and infrastructure have significantly decreased. However, all this is a temporary situation. As the standard of living of the population improved, the control of traffic flows in large cities has almost disappeared. Traffic jams cannot be avoided at all. Increasing the swing of public transport, which is currently considered as the only solution, or increasing the use of electric-powered cars, is a solution to the above issues, albeit somewhat. But this is only a solution to the transport problem. A sharp decrease in drinking water around the world is the most pressing problem of today.

Pollution of air and water as a result of urbanization, increased emissions are a growing problem of urban planning ecology. New diseases are emerging as a result of urban air pollution, mainly processes related to fossil fuels (energy sources extracted for heating buildings, industrial consumption), an increase in noise levels from the norm.

Typically, cities produce a unique ecosystem as a result of large consumption of energy, water, food and various raw materials. The city's ecosystem requires a special approach at the expense of huge energy consumption and waste. At the same time, it is necessary not to forget that as a result of the degradation of urban landscapes, water resources, depletion of fertile lands significantly affect the atmosphere of the city.

Urban ecology is a holistic understanding of city complexity and interacting factors, diverse feedback, and nonlinear dynamics of cities. Biodiversity - all living organisms, including plants, animals and microorganisms-is vital to human life. However, when we think about biodiversity, we rarely imagine a city. Nature is

often associated only with rural landscapes, but in fact there are many ecosystems and natural resources that preserve rich biodiversity in urban areas. We are immersed in nature, and yet we know very little about it [1].

Conclusion. As a modern solution to the problems of urban ecology, I can present the Smart City project. A smart city is an improvement in the exchange of information with the public, the automatic calculation of the ehtoyoji of the population in living conditions and their management using modern technologies. In this case, special attention is paid to the environmental efficiency of cities.

Several factors are used to determine whether a city is “smart”. They are as follows:

- Technology-based infrastructure;
- Environmental initiatives;
- High-performance public transport systems;
- Modern, future-oriented master plan of the city;
- People who can live and work in the city, use its resources wisely.

The effectiveness of the”smart city “increases the ability of the population to use new technologies, their” ecological culture ” and the state's strong confidence in the private sector. This relationship is very important because most of the work to create and maintain a digital environment based on data is done outside the government. Crowded street tracking equipment may include sensors from one company, cameras from another, and a server from another[2].

The Smart City project is a developed concept of how cities today have an efficient environmental infrastructure. Because, the "smart city" adapts and develops depending on the infrastructure in which it is located.

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